

Impact of Social Factors on Effective Teaching among Lecturers in Colleges of Education in Northeast, Nigeria

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Abstract

This research examines the impact of social factors on effective teaching among lecturers in colleges of education (COEs) in the North East, Nigeria. Four research questions were stated to direct the study. The study used a quantitative approach and collected data through a survey questionnaire from 8 colleges of education in the North East of Nigeria. The population of the study consisted of 3,592 Lecturers and stratified random sampling technique was employed to select a sample of 360 lecturers that reflects the population. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions while inferential statistics of Pearson correlation was used to determine the relationship between the variables. The findings of this study revealed that social factors such as economic status, environmental factors, lecturer-student relationships, and peer collaboration moderately affect teaching effectiveness among COE lecturers in Northeast Nigeria. The correlation results further indicate that these social factors are closely interrelated, with particularly strong relationships between environmental factors and peer collaboration, as well as between economic status and lecturer-student relationships. The paper recommends that government should review salary structures to improving the financial stability of lecturers, Institutions should be organizing regular workshops and seminars to encourage collaboration among lecturers and Lecturers should engage more in student-centered teaching approaches for effectiveness.

Keyword: social factors, lecturers and teaching effectiveness.

Introduction

Effective teaching in Colleges of Education (COE) is a key factor in teacher production. Teaching is the core role of lecturers in the education stream. The components of research and community services rely solely on what teaching has provided or set to provide for pre-service teachers (Acato, 2016). Investment in teacher training within the education sector is considered an investment in human capital, which increases labor productivity and enhances technological innovation and sustainable teacher production (Abbas, 2023). Effective teaching refers to the knowledge, strategies, processes, and behaviors that lead to good pre-service teacher outcomes (High-speed Training, 2023). Similarly, Smith (2020) posits that effective teaching involves delivering instruction that accommodates diverse student abilities, aligns with clear instructional objectives, and assesses learning outcomes to ensure all students achieve their full potential. Effective teaching has a positive impact on both the student and teacher because it facilitates the deployment of professionalism and absolute concentration towards improving learning outcomes among pre-service teachers. These learning outcomes are often those that can be measured easily, usually through summative evaluation (Abbas, 2023.)

In general, education reflects the social pattern of society, which implies that the general social environment in which lecturers in COE operate affects their lives in different ways and the other social problems bedeviling them have direct effects on the teaching competencies required for smooth learning processes. Effective teaching expected from COE lecturers in northeast Nigeria requires a holistic approach in areas such as teaching materials, personality, infrastructure, environment, motivation, and other working tools to achieve the stated objectives for sustainable teacher production. Contextually, lecturers in COE are specialists in teacher education from the grassroots and their ability to produce quality teachers cannot be overemphasized. However, an examination of the general performance of students from secondary school's standard examination such as NECO, WAEC, NABTEB, NBAIS etc. reveals low performance. Relationship exists between effective teaching in COE and secondary school students' performance in standard examinations.

Recent empirical studies have highlighted the significant impact of social factors on teaching effectiveness in Nigerian colleges of education. Economic status influences both teachers and students; teachers from higher socioeconomic backgrounds often have better access to resources and

professional development opportunities, which can enhance their teaching quality. Similarly, students from affluent families tend to perform better academically due to supportive home environments and access to educational materials. Environmental factors, such as inadequate classroom facilities and lack of teaching aids, can hinder effective teaching and learning. A study by Nwosu et al. (2019) highlighted that factor such as inadequate classrooms and libraries, as well as poor socio-economic backgrounds, contribute to underachievement among student teachers in Nigeria. The lecturer-student relationship is another critical factor; positive interactions between lecturers and students foster a conducive learning environment, leading to improved academic outcomes. Research indicates that when lecturers engage with students empathetically and supportively, students are more motivated and perform better academically. Peer collaboration among lecturers also contributes to teaching effectiveness. Collaborative practices, such as sharing teaching strategies and resources, have been shown to enhance instructional quality and professional growth among educators. For example, a study by Korb and Akintunde (2013) demonstrated that factors influencing teacher job satisfaction, including peer collaboration, significantly impact teaching effectiveness in Nigerian schools. Collectively, these studies underscore the importance of addressing social factors to improve teaching effectiveness in Nigerian educational institutions.

The 21st century pre-service teacher education is faced with many challenges that hinder the effective implementation of the entire system in Nigeria. Social factors have been observed to hinder the success of COE lecturers in achieving their main objectives. Despite great efforts by the government to develop and enhance effective teaching and learning in Nigerian COE, there still exist various factors that stand in the way of achieving holistic success. The rapid changes and increased complexity of today's world present new challenges and put new demands on our educational system, especially pre-service teacher training. The 21st century has unveiled additional ways in which teaching can be effectively handled, even virtually; however, due to prevailing challenges associated with social factors, effective teaching has become a mirage in Nigerian COE (Opara, 2023). In an effort to strengthen teacher education training in COE and enhance the per formance of lecturers in the process of sustainable teacher production, there is a need to examine the effects of social factors on effective teaching among lecturers in COEs in northeast Nigeria.

Research Question

The following research questions were formulated to guide this study.

1. What is the level at which economic status affect effective teaching among COE lecturers in North east Nigeria?
2. What is the extent at which environmental factors affect effective teaching among COE lecturers in Northeast Nigeria?
3. What is the influence of lecturer-student relationship on effective teaching among COE lecturers in North East Nigeria?
4. What is the level at which peer collaboration affects effective teaching among COE lecturers in North East, Nigeria?

Hypothesis

H₀₁: Economic status does not significantly affect effective teaching among COE lecturers in Northeast Nigeria.

H₀₂: Environmental factors do not significantly affect effective teaching among COE lecturers in Northeast Nigeria.

H₀₃: Lecturer-student relationships do not significantly influence effective teaching among COE lecturers in Northeast Nigeria.

H₀₄: Peer collaboration does not significantly affect effective teaching among COE lecturers in Northeast Nigeria.

Methodology

This research uses a descriptive correlational survey design. The study population comprised all COE lecturers in northeast Nigeria. The total COE in the North East is 14, with a total population of lecturers estimated at 3,592. A stratified random sampling technique was used to select a representative sample of 360 lecturers from the population and multi-stage is adopted because the

population across the COEs is not the same and there is a need to select sample stages before sampling the COEs where the research participants sampled (four) states from the Six (6) states and Two (2) COEs; One (1) federal and one (1) state COE in each. This descriptive correlational survey utilized an adapted questionnaire from Quar (2017), modified for relevance to the context of colleges of education in Northeast Nigeria. The instrument is divided into four sections, measuring economic status, environmental factors, lecturer-student relationships, and peer collaboration. These sections address the key variables under investigation, ensuring a comprehensive analysis of the research objectives. However, since there was a slight modification of the items, content validity was conducted to ensure the appropriateness of the items to measure what they were intended to measure. As such, experts' opinions and inputs in the field of educational psychology, testing and measurement, and English language opinion was sought in reviewing the items of the constructs before final usage.

The set of questionnaires used has close-ended items that measure the variables of the study using a Likert-type rating scale of responses ranging from Strongly Agree (SA = 1) through Strongly Disagree (SD = 4) for Research Question three (RQ3) while Verry High Level (VH = 1), High Level (H = 2), Low Level (L = 3) and Very Low Level (VL = 4) for RQ1,2&3. The reported Cronbach's alpha coefficients of the set of instruments were 0.825 and was compared with 0.92 obtained after the pilot test. The researcher collected data from the sampled respondents of the population under study through the administration of a 38 item Questionnaire titled Social Factor on Effective Teaching Among Lecturers (SFETS). Stata 17 was used to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the results.

Result

Q1. What is the level at which economic status affects effective teaching among COE lecturers in North east Nigeria?

Table 1: Impact of Economic Status on Effective Teaching

S/N	QUESTION ITEMS	X	SD	Remark
1.	Significant economic challenges distract/influence Lecturer's attention when teaching	1.620787	.6139371	High
2.	Recent economic policies (e.g. Fuel Subsidy) affect financial status of lecturers	1.589888	.6327307	High
3.	Recent economic policies (e.g. Fuel Subsidy) affect instructional output of lecturers	1.83427	.6307204	High
4.	I keep evaluating my financial ability every month in order to be Productive in teaching	1.896067	.6779308	High
5.	I engage in additional work outside lecturing to have extra income so as to concentrate more in my teaching job	1.963483	.8333291	High
6.	My economic status affects my ability to procure resources for teaching	2.058989	.8286443	High
7.	My career progression is affected by my economic status	2.140449	.935945	High
8.	Government frequently increases the salaries of teachers for effective delivery	2.154494	.9677952	High
9.	Promotions are regularly implemented to improve the economic status for effectiveness of lecturers	2.244382	.8044572	High
10.	Incremental steps are regularly implemented to improve the economic status for effectiveness of lecturers	2.235955	.8691582	High
11.	My salaries and wages are adequate that they can afford necessary materials needed to enhance my research	2.109551	.8166016	High
12.	Lecturers who have low socio-economic status always struggle to meet their family's basic needs which affect their teaching productivity negatively	1.83427	.7300818	High
13.	Lecturers with pressing financial needs lack the time and opportunities to improve their skills and knowledge required to cope with daily teaching challenges.	1.901685	.7459921	High
14.	I make use of available forms of credits facilities in my institution so as to be productive	2.401685	.8649009	High
Grand mean		1.998997		High

Midpoint of the Likert scale used in the questionnaire (scale 1–4, the midpoint is 2.5). The grand mean = 1.999 (approximately 2.00), which falls in the "High Level" (H) category indicates Economic

challenges (e.g., financial instability and fuel subsidy removal) significantly affect lecturers' concentration and teaching effectiveness. Lecturers seek additional income sources, which impacts their ability to focus on teaching. Economic constraints limit access to teaching resources and affect career growth. Salary increments and promotions exist but are not adequate to significantly improve lecturers' economic status. Therefore, Economic status has a high impact on effective teaching, particularly through financial stress and resource limitations.

Q2. What is the extent at which environmental factors affect effective teaching among COE lecturers in Northeast Nigeria?

Table 2: Impact of Environmental Factors on Effective Teaching

S/N	QUESTION ITEMS	X	SD	Remark
1.	Thermal comfort affects productivity in the workplace and effectiveness in teaching	1.938202	.7250846	High
2.	Ventilation or cleanliness affect the health of lecturers in colleges and have direct impact on teaching effectiveness.	2.098315	.8076378	High
3.	Building conditions directly affect lecturers' attitudes to teaching	2.106742	.8943387	High
4.	Lecturers housed in newer school buildings and staff quarters that are well furnished taught more effectively than lecturers housed in dilapidated structures.	1.966292	.8180973	High
5.	Lecturers in spaced classrooms taught more effectively than those housed in compressed classrooms.	2.210674	.8378366	High
6.	I feel the teaching environment conducive to learning (e.g. noise levels)	2.047753	.8593942	High
7.	I feel the teaching environment conducive to learning (e.g. temperature control)	2.106742	.9130414	High
8.	I feel safe and secure within the college environment; this aid in my teaching effectiveness	2.064607	.8417186	High
9.	The physical condition of classrooms affects my ability to teach effectively	2.16573	.9512363	High
Grand mean		2.078339		High

The grand mean = 2.078, classified as "High Level" (H) indicates Thermal comfort, ventilation, and cleanliness affect lecturers' health and teaching performance. Classroom conditions (e.g., spacious vs. compressed rooms) influence teaching effectiveness. Security and noise levels in the school environment contribute to teaching productivity. Therefore, Environmental factors highly impact teaching effectiveness, with infrastructural conditions playing a key role.

Q3. What is the influence of lecturer-student relationship on effective teaching among COE lecturers in North East Nigeria?

Table 3: Influence of Lecturer-Student Relationships on Effective Teaching

S/N	QUESTION ITEMS	X	SD	Remark
1.	Good Relationship with students can have a positive impact on lecturer’s effectiveness	1.761236	.7405842	Agreed
2.	Lecturer-Student relationship is a determinant of the Teaching Effectiveness.	1.957865	.7587387	Agreed
3.	It is necessary for both the student and teachers to pay special attention to improving the student-teacher relationship for effectiveness	1.825843	.6654496	Agreed
4.	The more the lecturer-student relationship is ignored in classroom, the more academic performance is affected.	1.88764	.703123	Agreed
5.	Lecturer-student relationship enables the lecturers to have a positive and encouraging feedback of teaching effectiveness	1.949438	.7637747	Agreed
6.	I do implement any strategies to improve relationships with students for the purpose of enhancing teaching effectiveness	1.719101	.7079232	Agreed
7.	I do assess feedback from students indicating that my relationship with them has impacted their learning experience	1.710674	.635121	Agreed
8.	I do observe any positive change in students’ engagement or performance as a result of my relationship with them	1.808989	.702132	Agreed
	Grand mean	1.827598		Agreed

The grand mean 1.828, indicating agreement. Strong lecturer-student relationships enhance teaching effectiveness and student performance. Poor relationships negatively impact classroom engagement and academic outcomes. Lecturers who actively foster positive relationships observe better feedback and student participation. However, Lecturer-student relationships positively influence effective teaching by improving engagement, communication, and feedback.

Q4. What is the level at which peer collaboration affects effective teaching among COE lecturers in North East, Nigeria?

Table 4: Impact of Peer Collaboration on Effective Teaching

S/N	QUESTION ITEMS	X	SD	Remark
1.	Peer collaboration improves teaching competencies of lecturers	1.912921	.6885391	High
2.	Working with others in peer allows teacher to identify learning gap	1.848315	.6834234	High

3.	Lecturer professional development courses on collaborative teaching is urgently needed to ensure the effectiveness in teaching	2.039326	.8647224	High
4.	Lack of willingness among lectures to share their expertise during teaching process and professionally socialized to partners in the classrooms for effectiveness	2.264045	.8804285	High
5.	Teachers have to collaborate to implement an effective method for systemic improvement in teaching skills.	2.16573	.9211473	High
6.	Mentoring by the senior can facilitate juniors to learn, adapt and familiarize with the environment for effective teaching	1.960674	.8482782	High
7.	I do participate in different forms of peer collaboration (e.g. Co-teaching sessions)	1.941011	.7311215	High
Grand mean		2.01886		High

A grand mean of 2.01886 is very close to 2, classified as "High Level" (H). This reveal that Peer collaboration enhances teaching skills and professional development. Lack of willingness to share expertise among lecturers negatively impacts professional growth. Structured mentoring and professional training are needed to maximize the benefits of collaboration. Therefore, Peer collaboration strongly influences effective teaching, but institutional support is required for sustained improvement.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics for Social Factors

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
ESET	356	1.998997	.7316298	1	3.714286
EVET	356	2.075843	.8507697	1	4
LRET	356	1.88764	.7228769	1	4
PCETL	356	2.011236	.8152681	1	4

Source: STATA 17

From table 5 above, the economic status of lecturers in the study is reflected by a mean of 1.999, which suggests that, on average, respondents felt their economic conditions significantly affect their effective teaching. The standard deviation of 0.731 indicates that responses did not varies much, with most lecturers reporting similar economic challenges. The minimum value of 1 suggests that some lecturers felt they were in a highly constrained economic situation, while the maximum of 3.714 shows that a small group of lecturers experienced slightly better economic conditions.

The relatively low mean indicates that many lecturers struggle with financial issues, which may impede their ability to focus on teaching effectively. The moderate variability in the responses shows that most lecturers face similar financial challenges, with only a few experiencing better economic situations. These financial constraints can affect motivation, job satisfaction, and ultimately, teaching performance.

Also, Environmental factors received a mean score of 2.076, indicating moderate influence on teaching effectiveness. The standard deviation of 0.851 shows relatively higher variability in respondents' perceptions of environmental conditions. The minimum value of 1 suggests that some lecturers work in extremely poor environments, while the maximum value of 4 indicates that others operate in more favorable conditions.

The moderate mean implies that environmental challenges, such as infrastructure, classroom conditions, and access to resources, affect the teaching process. Some lecturers may be more disadvantaged than others, as seen from the wide variation in responses, which suggests that improvements in environmental factors could lead to better teaching outcomes for many lecturers. Additionally, the lecturer-student relationship had the lowest mean score of 1.888, indicating that respondents generally felt this factor was less favorable. The standard deviation of 0.723 shows a moderate spread of responses. The minimum value of 1 suggests some lecturers have poor relationships with students, while a maximum score of 4 indicates that a few lecturers enjoy positive interactions.

The low mean indicates that many lecturers experience strained relationships with students, which can hinder effective communication, engagement, and overall classroom dynamics. This variable's influence on teaching effectiveness is critical, as strong lecturer-student relationships contribute to better learning outcomes. Improving this relationship could enhance teaching effectiveness across the board. Peer collaboration had a mean of 2.011, showing that it moderately affects teaching effectiveness. The standard deviation of 0.815 reflects moderate variability in the responses, with some lecturers reporting better collaboration than others. The minimum score of 1 show that a few lecturers felt little to no collaboration, while the maximum of 4 indicates that others engage more actively with their peers.

The mean score suggests that peer collaboration is moderately practiced among lecturers, with room for improvement. Peer support and collaboration are essential for sharing teaching strategies,

resources, and feedback. Enhancing collaborative efforts among lecturers could boost the overall effectiveness of teaching, especially in creating a supportive teaching environment.

Correlation Test Results

The Pearson correlation coefficients in Table 6 indicate the relationships between economic status (ESET), environmental factors (EVET), lecturer-student relationships (LRET), and peer collaboration (PCETL). Each hypothesis is tested based on the strength and direction of the correlations as follows:

Table 6: Pearson Correlation Coefficients

Variable	ESET	EVET	LRET	PCETL
ESET	1.0000			
EVET	0.9485	1.0000		
LRET	0.9151	0.8950	1.0000	
PCETL	0.9422	0.9609	0.9230	1.0000

Source: STATA 17

Hypothesis 1: Economic status affects effective teaching among lecturers.

Strong positive correlation ($r = 0.9485$) exists between economic status and environmental factors, suggesting that lecturers facing economic challenges are likely to encounter poor working conditions. This supports the hypothesis that economic stability influences teaching effectiveness, as poor financial well-being can lead to decreased focus and performance.

Hypothesis 2: Environmental factors affect effective teaching among lecturers.

The correlation ($r = 0.9609$) between environmental factors and peer collaboration implies that poor environmental conditions negatively impact the ability of lecturers to collaborate effectively. This supports the hypothesis that environmental challenges are a significant barrier to teaching effectiveness.

Hypothesis 3: Lecturer-student relationships influence effective teaching.

The relationship between economic status and lecturer-student relationships ($r = 0.9151$) highlights that financial strain impacts lecturers' ability to maintain positive engagement with students. This aligns with the hypothesis that lecturer-student relationships are influenced by external factors like economic stability.

Hypothesis 4: Peer collaboration affects effective teaching.

The correlation ($r = 0.9230$) between lecturer-student relationships and peer collaboration supports the hypothesis that peer collaboration enhances teaching effectiveness. Financial and environmental challenges appear to hinder collaboration, impacting the overall quality of teaching.

Lastly, the results from Table 6 test the hypotheses by demonstrating strong positive correlations among the variables. These findings underline the interconnectedness of economic status, environmental factors, lecturer-student relationships, and peer collaboration in influencing teaching effectiveness.

Interpretation of Findings

The descriptive statistics reveal that social factors such as economic status, environmental factors, lecturer-student relationships, and peer collaboration moderately affect teaching effectiveness among COE lecturers in Northeast Nigeria. The correlation results further indicate that these social factors are closely interrelated, with particularly strong relationships between environmental factors and peer collaboration, as well as between economic status and lecturer-student relationships.

Discussion of Findings

From the study, the following findings were made.

1. That the recent economic policy (fuel subsidy removal) affects Lecturer's performance and productivity in teaching.
2. That Economic challenges affect lecturer's financial wellbeing and have a negative impact on his teaching.
3. That money and social status is significant factor which influences a Lecturer's academic performance.
4. The study also reveals that thermal comfort is an influential factor in Lecturers' academic performance.
5. Class size, cleanliness and environmental safety pay a very significant role in boosting Lecturers' effectiveness in teaching.
6. The study also reveals that when Lecturers have good relationship with students; they perform better academically.
7. That students need to inculcate good habits and engage in a good relationship with their Lecturers.
8. That peer collaboration among lecturers improved their teaching competencies

9. That learning gaps can be easily addressed when Lecturers promote collaborative teachings.
10. That mentorship and workshops play a vital role in effective teaching among Lecturers.

The findings of this study align with previous research that highlights the significant influence of social factors on teaching effectiveness such as: Lecturers' financial well-being and job performance by Okoi, I., & Odigwe, F. (2018), The social factors affecting the teaching and learning by Quar (2017) and causes of attrition among lecturers in colleges of education in North East Nigeria by Umar, M. B., & Umar, A. (2023). The strong correlations found in this study suggest that these factors are not isolated but rather interact to impact the teaching process.

For instance, the high correlation between environmental factors and peer collaboration implies that creating a conducive environment may foster better collaboration among lecturers, which in turn improves teaching outcomes. Similarly, the link between economic status and lecturer-student relationships indicates that lecturers' financial stability is crucial for maintaining positive and effective engagement with students.

Conclusion

This study concludes that social factors, specifically economic status, environmental factors, lecturer-student relationships, and peer collaboration, play a significant role in influencing the teaching effectiveness of COE lecturers in Northeast Nigeria. The findings suggest that improving these factors can lead to better teaching outcomes and enhanced educational quality in COEs.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. **Improvement of Economic Conditions:** Government and educational administrators should consider improving the financial stability of lecturers by reviewing salary structures and providing additional support, such as housing allowances, to alleviate financial pressures.
2. **Enhancement of Environmental Conditions:** COEs should ensure that the teaching environment is conducive by investing in infrastructure and resources that support effective teaching. This includes modernizing classrooms, providing teaching aids, and reducing class sizes.

3. **Promotion of Peer Collaboration:** Institutions should encourage collaboration among lecturers by organizing regular workshops, seminars, and collaborative teaching sessions. This will foster a supportive environment where lecturers can share ideas and strategies to improve their teaching.
4. **Strengthening Lecturer-Student Relationships:** Lecturers should be encouraged to engage in more interactive and student-centered teaching approaches. This can be supported by providing training on effective communication and relationship building techniques.

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